

STUDIES AND RESEARCH REGARDING THE ONLINE MARKETING AND THE RELATED CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

Purpose – *This paper aims at highlighting the importance of online marketing in the Internet and e-commerce age, providing, at the same time, a basic understanding of the main techniques that can help a business stand out organically (for free) in the online environment.*

Methodology/approach – *This paperwork comprises a marketing study on the consumer behavior in relation to online marketing. This marketing research is a quantitative one, the survey being the method used, while the questionnaire is its research instrument. The sampling method used is a random one, based on accessibility. A sample of 331 natural persons has been surveyed.*

Keywords: *Marketing research, consumer behavior, SEO (Search Engine Optimization), blog and social media.*

Introduction

Nowadays, the companies can no longer ignore the importance of online marketing in their effort to be always one step ahead of their competition. The digital age has brought the access to an unlimited variety of products, which, in its turn, has radically changed consumer behavior.

In order to be able to choose from among all these products, nowadays consumers turn to the online environment, searching for useful information and advice, instead of commercials. Likewise, they are choosing more and more online shopping, for convenience. Moreover, the Z Generation, the new demographic group that will represent future customers, expect everything to be done online. Thus, it will become extremely difficult for the companies which do not yet exist online to attract them.

In this context, this paperwork is meant to be an online marketing introductory guide, useful to any manager or entrepreneur interested in this matter. Therefore, this work features the three main instruments used in order to bring organic traffic (free of charge) to any website: SEO, blog and social media.

SEO, the search engine optimization, represents all the actions taken to get a web page appear among the first pages, as a search engine result. SEO includes both technical aspects and content-related aspects. The company's blog can be used as a valuable source of information and as an efficient way to communicate with the customers. The external links to the blog articles contribute, to a large extent, to the SEO efforts. Since it is getting more and more popular, social media is a good way to build a name for the company's brand and to create a community around the company's products. The attention received by social media also contributes to the SEO.

The applicability of all these theoretical concepts is practically proven by using a study on the consumer behavior in relation to online marketing.

Methodology

This marketing research is a quantitative one, the survey being the method used, while the questionnaire is its research instrument.

The purpose of the marketing research is that of studying the consumer behavior in relation to the online marketing.

The data sources are primary sources, since the information comes directly from the people surveyed. For the distribution of the questionnaire, the Google Forms online platform has been used.

For the questionnaire, we have used: dichotomous questions, frequency scale questions (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never) and importance scale questions (very important, important, neutral, less important, not at all important) and identification questions. The questionnaire has 25 questions, six of which are demographic questions.

The pretesting of the questionnaire has been done on a number of five subjects and the results have not been included in the final data. Following the pretesting, certain questions have been amended, some questions have been removed and others have been added. The final survey has been conducted on 331 natural persons, their selection being carried out according to a random sampling, based on accessibility.

Results

Based on the results, we can say that 91% of the surveyed people shop online regularly, as compared to only 9%, who do not.

Among the people who have answered „Yes” to the first question, most of them use to buy products online once every 2 or 3 months (37%), followed by several times per month (24%) and once per month (20%).

The overwhelming majority of 98% of the people surveyed use internet to look for information about certain products they are interested in. We can say that it is important for a company to make the details, information and advice about its products available online.

The answers received show that the mobile phone is the most often used device for searching online information (59%), followed by the PC or the laptop (39%). Only a small percentage of the subjects surveyed use the tablet for such a thing (2%).

Although, as expected, most of the consumers who look for online information, also buy the products through the Internet (65%), a significant percentage of the people surveyed would rather make the final purchase in a physical store, when possible (35%). Therefore, a strategy that combines online presence with „brick-and-mortar” type shops is the most advantageous strategy for a company these days.

Most people in the group surveyed, namely 83%, believe that the assertion „The more expensive a product is, the more I look up information about it before purchasing it.” Is a true one. It is a good thing for the companies to provide as much information as possible about such products, as reviews, tutorials, blog articles etc.

The most important factors in the consumers’ decision to buy certain products are, in the following order: de reviews/other consumer opinions (274 votes), comparison between product specifications (230), video tutorials or articles featuring how the product can be used (121), pictures of the product (74), reviews/opinions of public figures/influencers (31), the commercial of the product (13). Thus, the commercials have considerably less impact upon the consumers as compared to the reviews, tutorials and online articles.

89% of the people surveyed look for a company, a product or a restaurant they have just heard of or which is new for them online, proving the importance of a company’s presence on the web, especially at the beginning, when it is trying hard to build a name and be renown.

Most of the answers to this question have constantly fluctuated during the questionnaire, so as, in the end, the assertion „Nowadays, if a company does not have a website, it is not to be trusted.” is generally

considered as being true, (51% vs. 49%). Although the difference is a small one, the companies who still want to remain competitive should seriously consider the fact that they could lose half of the potential clients by ignoring this basic online marketing aspect, namely the company's website.

83% of the people taking part in this study confirm that when looking for something on Google, if they do not find relevant information on the first two pages, they change the search words and try again.

A fairly large number of subjects read the online articles completely, always or often (142). Nevertheless, in order to maximize the number of readers and online articles on the company's blog, it would be a good idea for the company to take into consideration also those people who do not do this regularly (189), by creating articles that are easy to scan according to the methods presented in chapter III.

The clickbait-type articles are seen with distrust by the readers and are a good way to attract them. Besides the 86% of the subjects surveyed, who believe that such articles "seem to try to trick you," 11% have filled in: "They drive me crazy." „Are horrible!" „I'm sure they're useless." etc.

202 of the 331 people taking part in the study believe that optimizing a website for the mobile phone is very important, strengthening the results obtained at question number 4. For a pleasant experience of a website's user, it is not enough for the website to be well done exclusively for the desktop version.

As we all know, most of the Romanian consumers use social media. 96% of the people surveyed do it regularly, as compared to only 4%, who do not use social media.

It is not surprising that the most used social media are Facebook (274 votes) and Instagram (170). The utilization rate of Twitter, LinkedIn or Snapchat cannot yet be compared to that of the first two, although in other countries these are much more popular (for instance, Twitter is used extensively in the United States).

Most of the people taking part in this study said that their interest in certain products increases when the said products are shown in pictures, videos, stories or other posts on social media (64%). The relationships with the influencers or the customer promotion crowdsourcing are those that help the most, so as the content in these posts is as natural as possible.

The targeted/customized online commercials rarely (77 votes) or even very rarely (165) attract visits on the product presentation pages. Therefore, online promotion should be done organically and as natural as possible.

In the end, a few coordinates related to the profile of the studied sample will also be presented.

65% of the people surveyed have been females and the remaining 35% have been males.

Most of the subjects, 59%, were aged between 24 and 39 years when the study has been conducted, being part of the Millennial generation. The following age categories, according to the number of participants to the study, are: the Z Generation (28%), the X Generation (11%) and the Baby Boomers Generation (2%).

Most of the (92%) investigated people come from an urban environment.

The three main occupations of the people surveyed are, in order: salaried employee (67%), pupil or student (25%) and entrepreneur/freelancer (4%). The emergence of the third category shows the fact that entrepreneurship and freelancing also get a running start in our country.

Most of the subjects have Bachelor studies (47%). A pretty significant percentage is represented also by those people who have completed the master studies (33%).

The main fields of practice of the subjects surveyed, when the study has been conducted, are, in order: IT (22%), engineering (17%), marketing (15%), healthcare (11%) and economic (10%). The remaining percentages have other practice fields, such as: education, architecture, psychology, design, law.

From the point of view of the net monthly income per each family member of the people surveyed, it has been noted that 29% fall within the 3.001 – 5.000 RON category and a quarter fall within the 2.001 – 3.000 RON categories and within the 5.000 RON category respectively. Likewise, it is important to

mention the fact that the question being optional, only 299 of the overall number of 331 have answered these questions.

Conclusions

With the advent of the Internet, the world has radically changed. The abundance age, brought by the fact that the Internet makes any kind of product available to anyone and anywhere, had a significant influence upon the consumers' behavior. They no longer trust as much as before the traditional commercials; instead, they look for useful information and advice, which would help them making decisions about the products they want to purchase. Furthermore, the consumers turn their attention, more and more, towards online shops. All these make the companies turn to online marketing, even more so if we consider the fact that the Z Generation, the future clients, expect everything to be done in a digital environment. Any company ignoring these aspects will have problems in keeping up with its competition.

SEO (Search Engine Optimization) is the most important aspect when it comes to online visibility of a business. Regardless of how good the content of a company's website is, it cannot be appreciated if it cannot be found. SEO refers to all the efforts that make a webpage appear on the first pages with results for a certain Google search. The technical aspects are equally important as using the key words searched by the users or as obtaining the external links.

The company's blog is a very powerful online marketing instrument, contributing both to the SEO and to the direct communication with the customers of the potential clients. In order for it to be efficient, one must take into consideration certain article editing rules, based on the fact that people read the online content in a different manner as compared to the content of a book or a magazine. Due to the fact that the users look for usefulness and, many times, they make their search in a hurry, their attention in an online environment is limited. This is why an online optimized article is easier to read, providing exactly the information that the readers are looking for, in a format that they can easily scan with their own eyes.

Social media are increasingly being used, both worldwide and in Romania, being an excellent way to increase a company's online visibility and a brand's fame. The choice of the best social media for the promotion of a business is done depending on the consumers the said business wants to attract, the most popular being Facebook and Instagram. In order to avoid getting the opposite effect, social media promotion must comply with a certain format the users are used to and expect to see. A content as natural as possible, coming from other users or from trustworthy people has a great impact upon consumers. Therefore, the collaboration with influencers or the use of the content created by the clients are efficient social media promotion techniques.

The relevance of all these theoretical aspects has been proven in practice by using a 25 question questionnaire, for which, 331 answers have been received. 91% of the people surveyed shop online regularly, while 98% look for the online information they are interested in. Most of the subjects, 83%, do not get past the second page of results when they are looking for something on Google, proving the importance of the SEO. The traditional commercials have a much less influence upon the consumer decisions as compared to the video tutorials or articles that show the way in which the product can be used (15 vs. 121 votes). Moreover, 96% of those taking part in the study use social media and 64% of them say that it is very likely for them to be interested in a product they have seen in a picture, in a video or in a post on these social media.

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